

DEVELOPING THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS TO USE MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10565858>

Annotation: This article considers a number of issues related to the effective training of teachers in the use of mobile technologies in the educational process at the current stage of development of the local education system. Before starting the conversation about the main topic, it is shown that the widespread introduction of mobile technologies is one of the most important conditions that help to further modernize the educational process. In addition, the importance of developing appropriate competencies in the teacher in terms of more effective integration of relevant technologies into the educational process is shown. For many teachers, characteristic deficiencies in their development are demonstrated. Necessary measures are determined to eliminate these shortcomings. In order to increase the effectiveness of the development of relevant competences, possible methods of modernization of the existing additional education system of teachers are proposed.

Key words: mobile technologies in education, teacher training courses, teacher tutoring, ir competence, mobile competence

Introduction.

Today, the main features of the development of modern society, including Russia, are mainly related to its transition to the post-industrial stage. In the new model society, the graduates of the basic general and secondary general education system do not have ready knowledge, but they have developed skills and abilities related to the ability to independently search for information, to act in almost unlimited information flows skills are of particular importance.

Accordingly, the role of the teacher also changes. In his professional activity, the ability to show students the way to independently obtain the necessary information, to "*teach them to learn*" using modern information and telecommunications, including mobile technologies, is of particular importance.

In this regard, it is not surprising that issues related to the wide introduction of mobile technologies into the educational process occupy an important place in the works of teachers. At the same time, according to many teacher-researchers and practitioners, the introduction of such technologies mainly determines the success of further improvement of the local education system.

In turn, an important condition for the successful integration of mobile technologies into the educational process is the development of appropriate competences among teachers. This article is devoted to this problem.

Presentation of the main material of the article. The term "*teacher's mobile competence*" introduced by the American researcher G. Dudney refers to the level of knowledge and skills necessary for the effective use of mobile technologies in the implementation of educational

activities by the teacher. This component of the competence of a modern teacher is at the same time an integral part of his information communication competence. It is a system of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to evaluate the impact of mobile technologies on the effectiveness of the educational process and to develop a methodology for their successful integration.

From the point of view of the main topic of the review of this article, the results of the survey on the use of mobile technologies in the professional activities of teachers seem interesting (*table. 1*).

1-table.

<u>Frequency of use</u>	<u>Percentage of teachers</u>
<i>Use mobile technologies in professional activities</i>	98
<i>Regularly</i>	80
<i>Several times a month</i>	18
<i>Use mobile technologies, including to organize independent work</i>	1
<i>Do not use mobile technologies in professional activities</i>	2

Table 1. Use of mobile technologies in professional activities by school teachers.

The widespread use of mobile technologies by the majority of modern Russian teachers noted in the table is largely explained by the installation of interactive whiteboards in a number of educational organizations, as well as the mass distribution of mobile devices among students.

On the other hand, very few teachers, unfortunately, use mobile technologies to organize students' independent work. In addition, only half of the teachers are trying to organize educational work using mobile technologies, offering students special tasks aimed at wide use of the latter. Consequently, the potential of mobile technologies in the modern school environment is often not sufficiently disclosed.

Accordingly, it is necessary to increase the mobile competence of teachers at this stage of the development of the local education system. The latter should be focused primarily on the development of skills and abilities, which can be divided into three categories.

At the same time, it should be noted that at the current stage of the development of the education staff training system, attention is often paid to the technical component in the organization of relevant courses. Therefore, in order to effectively increase the mobile competence of teachers in the additional education system, not only the specific aspects of the use of mobile technologies in the educational process, but also their potential in terms of having a beneficial effect on the educational process attention should also be paid to the motivation to learn.

It is important to organize tutoring support in the sense of developing mobile competence of teachers. Tutors accompanying the teacher's professional development process on the basis of the educational institution thus ensure the implementation of the individual professional development direction of each teacher. This also applies to the effective use of mobile technologies in their professional activities.

In order to improve the mobile skills of teachers, on the basis of tutoring schools, teachers should conduct trainings on mastering different models of using mobile technologies in the educational process, introduce teaching staff to forms of distance education, as well as training in the relevant field can organize various competitions, seminars, "round talks" dedicated to methodological developments.

Tutors can be winners and laureates of all project competitions on relevant topics, participants of online conferences or networking events.

In turn, effective integration of mobile technologies is possible with a certain level of development of mobile competence among modern teachers.

This component of the modern teacher's qualification is a system of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to evaluate the impact of mobile technologies on the effectiveness of the educational process, to develop a methodology for their successful integration. Despite the widespread use of such technologies by many modern teachers, at the moment we can talk about the presence of a number of problems that make their integration into the educational process difficult.

For example, very few teachers use mobile technologies to organize students' independent work. In addition, only half of modern teachers create educational work using them and offer students special tasks aimed at wide use of these types of devices and programs.

Conclusions.

We can conclude from the above that today many teachers-researchers and practitioners consider the introduction of mobile technologies into the educational process as one of the main conditions that ensure its further improvement.

Accordingly, it is necessary to carry out large-scale work on the development of mobile competence of teachers. One of the ways to achieve the relevant results is the organization of course activities, in which the main focus should be on encouraging students to learn the possibilities of mobile technologies that allow to improve the quality of the educational process. A promising way to increase the mobile competence of modern teachers is their tutoring support. This allows teachers to implement individual trajectories of development of this component of their professional competence.

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